

FUNCTIONAL ELEMENTS OF TEXTILES IN THE MODERN INTERIOR OF HOTEL AND COUNTRY HOUSES

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Annotation. The article is devoted to the symbolic and functional role of textiles, its relationship with the modern hotel and country houses interior. This knowledge is especially necessary for understanding the modern culture of tourist complex design. The trends in the development of the art of textiles appear when studying the functional features of the spatial environment of the dwelling of Uzbekistan, since it is here that textiles show their ro

Keywords: textiles, housing, design, interior, tourism, weaving.

A major role in the creation of the objective and functional environment of the residential interior in Central Asia, throughout the history of many civilizations, was assigned to various types of textiles. This role has not lost its significance at the present time. Through the aesthetic organization of the space of human life, textiles are associated with the spiritual and artistic components of culture.

Significant changes in the subject equipment of modern residential buildings in recent decades are very important indicators of the development of design and its active impact on humans. With the help of design, you can transform the appearance of the room, give the interior a mood and completely change the stylistic direction.

The change in the typological and compositional characteristics of modern residential interiors entails the transformation of the textiles used in them.¹ The residential interior has become a kind of image characteristic that determines the lifestyle. These factors influenced the expansion of individual design and, after it, the decoration of the residential interior, which by the beginning of the twenty-first century was being revived as a separate area of professional activity, which was provoked by the need for a comprehensive solution to the living space, the formation of its image and style.

The figurative aspect today becomes one of the main ones in solving the subject-spatial environment of the residential interior, including its textile component. So, research on this issue is relevant in connection with the emergence of new architectural forms and changes in the typology of residential interiors, which naturally led to an increase in functional varieties of textiles that require classification and description.

In accordance with the foregoing, the theoretical justification of the modern approach to the subject-spatial content of the dwelling becomes a necessary area of scientific research.

Moreover, over the post-Soviet 4 decades, quite a lot of experience has been accumulated in creating both unique works of modern textile art and synthetic solutions for textile decoration of the modern living environment in Uzbekistan, which require generalization and analysis.

For the most part, the question of the role of textiles in the spatial organization of the interior was analyzed on the example of the use of carpet weaving, palyaks, suzane, zhulhirs. The development of this art form in the historical context, from the standpoint of the author's performance, the problem of synthesis of **carpet weaving** - tapestry with the interior on the material of both domestic and foreign experience.

¹ Khabibullina S. K. Textile as a means of forming the interior of a modern dwelling: dis. Cand. Art History: 17.00.04. Ekaterinburg, 2011.

A significant amount of practical material, consisting of many disparate objects, is generalized, for the first time subjected to a comprehensive analysis and is represented by a systematic picture of the development of modern environmental textiles. The results of the study change the traditional ideas in the field of textile design: interior textiles are considered as a synthetic direction in the field of related disciplines – architecture, arts and crafts, textile design.

The complexity of the study makes it possible **to introduce new objects of textile art into scientific circulation: "ceiling", "wall", "textile furniture", "textile sculpture", etc.**

The range of style directions of modern textile interior decoration is interesting. The material presented in the dissertation refers to the post-Soviet period, which has not yet become the subject of in-depth scientific study. For example: to the culture of the bed, the main types of which were cotton mattresses - kurpacha, blankets and pillows was very high, since these things characterized the prosperity of the owners of the house. In addition, etiquette norms required a decent level of reception of guests, who were seated on mattresses covered with expensive silk and semi-silk Central Asian fabrics. Nomads bought such kurpachi in the markets, but they themselves made mattresses from cloth and velvet, often decorating them with embroidery. A special style distinguished kurpacha, sewn in the patchwork technique kurak, which was considered a magical protective agent in the region.²

So, the main touch of the design project, which should create a finished look of the room, **is filling it with textiles**. When decorating a guest house, fabrics have very diverse possibilities: they are expressive and do not require much labor when replacing.

² Нодир Бинафша – искусствовед. Роль текстильной культуры в конструировании национальной идентичности Узбекистана и Казахстана.

Textiles make it possible to give the interior the romance of ethnicity, historical addressability. Textile accessories contribute a lot to the creation of comfort. Without a competent semantic under the fabric of it, the interior will not look attractive.

The disclosure of the general picture of the development of modern interior textiles within the framework of the article does not allow us to dwell in detail on its individual trends, which should become objects for further scientific research.

This article discusses the following trends:

1. The functions of textiles: the organization of space, social, spiritual, compensatory, ceremonial in conjunction with the fundamental (artistic and utilitarian) - most fully reveal the specifics of the modern residential interior.

The function of organizing space in terms of importance can be attributed to the main functions of textiles.

2. The main methods of interaction of textiles with modern residential interiors are to identify the tectonics of the interior, as well as the real and illusory transformation of its space-planning structure. The means by which these interactions are carried out are various types of interior textiles.

3. The author's classification includes the concept of interior textiles, its types, subspecies and typology. The concept of "interior textiles" is revealed in the multicomponent unity of its types involved in the textile decoration of the interior.

1. The main types of interior textiles have been established: textile materials and textile objects (three-dimensional and planar) and its subspecies.

1. The typology of interior textiles is associated with the nature of its functioning in the interior space, with design and plastic features: stationary, mobile and transformable textile objects.

1. The development of domestic textile art is subject to the general laws of world artistic practice.

4. Modern stylistic trends of textile compositions of the interior are associated with the main stylistic directions of architecture in line with the postmodern

interpretation - using reconstructions of historical styles (historicism), ethnic trends, neo-eclecticism, minimalism as a direction in demand in the light of the trends of the new project culture.

5. The classification of modern textile materials shows a significant expansion of the range of manual and industrial textiles. And active experimentation in the field of shaping and ornamentation. Any object of interior textiles is able to acquire the quality of a representative author's product in the modern design culture.

By the nature of the artistic features of textiles and the methods of its manufacture, the following division is proposed:

**a/author's representative textiles (or the result of studio creative activity),
b/industrial textiles, c/handicrafts.**

Thus, the formed approach to interior design as a decoratively completed space determined the attitude to any type of textile as a uniquely significant object.

The utilitarian function of textiles in the modern environmental situation is understood broadly and correlates with the relevant requirements of the hotel interior: its color and ornamental preferences, its orientation towards certain artistic or sacred values. However, with all the broadness of the attitude to this function, the qualitative characteristics of textiles, the expediency of its use remain the most important.

The function of textiles is determined, first of all, by the degree of its participation in the spatial and role organization of the hotel interior.

Reference literature

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